

Effect of fungicides on BPH hatching, mortality, and percentage of *M. anisopliae* infection. For each test vertical bars sharing a common letter are not significantly different using Duncan's multiple range test.

insects and plants were sprayed with 2 ml of 0.10% benomyl or edifenphos. Living insects in each cage were recorded 1 d after the last fungicide application.

In the third test, we studied the effect of the fungicides on *M. anisopliae*. Infected BPH adults which were covered with whitish to greenish spores of the fungus were collected in the greenhouse and placed on moist filter paper in a petri dish. Each dish was sprayed with 1 ml of 0.10% benomyl, edifenphos, or water. Twenty-four hours after treatment, the BPH with fungus spores were placed in a flask and thoroughly mixed with 20 cc distilled water containing 0.05% detergent. The spore solutions were sprayed on 20 of 2d- and 3d-instar BPH nymphs caged on 35-d-old potted

plants enclosed with a mylar cage. Each potted plant was sprayed with 2 ml of the solution. Seven days after spraying, the number of live BPH/cage was recorded. Treatments in each of the three tests were replicated four times.

Benomyl had no adverse effect on hatching, but edifenphos reduced hatching 34% below that with water (see figure). Benomyl was safe to BPH nymphs, producing mortality similar to that of water. Edifenphos caused 100% mortality. When nymphs were sprayed with the spore suspension, percentage of fungus-infected BPH was reduced from 33% in the control to 16% in the benomyl treatment. We are now using benomyl to control *M. anisopliae* in the BPH rearing program in wet season. □

Comparative observations of rice insect populations on indica and japonica rices

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We studied insect pest and predator population dynamics on indica and japonica rices in 1976-77 maha at Tismada, Sri Lanka, in pesticide-free fields. Two 10 × 2-m fields were transplanted on the same day, one with H-9 (indica) and one with Koshihikari (japonica). Both varieties are susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. Koshihikari is moderately resistant to stem borer (SB) *Chilo suppressalis*.

Insects were collected twice weekly until harvest by making 30 sweeps with a 36-cm butterfly net across the 2 fields. In the laboratory, specimens were killed, separated, and counted.

BPH, grasshopper, and *Leptispa pygmaea* populations did not differ. *Sogatella furcifera* was more abundant on the indica at early growth, but populations equalized at later stages. The GLH population was similar at

Comparative population fluctuation of two insect pests (*Nephotettix virescens* and *Leptocoris oratorius*) on two types (indica and japonica) of rice varieties.

early growth, but after heading was 10 times greater on the japonica (see figure). Cicadella spectra population was similar to that of GLH, being five times greater on the japonica after heading. There were few *Recilia dorsalis* on either variety, and slightly more *Thaia subrufa* on the indica at all stages. The *Leptocoris oratorius* population was highest and lasted longest on the japonica because it headed early. The indica had a tenfold larger population of the predator *Ophionea indica*. □

Crop loss in deepwater rice caused by yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We studied YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* infestation and control in deepwater rice in 1982. In mid-Aug, when there were many moths, we sprayed monocrotophos 250 g ai/ha from a boat. YSB infestation was significantly reduced (see table).